

CFD AND THERMAL ANALYSIS OF GAS TURBINE BLADES USING HIGH-TEMPERATURE ALLOYS AND CERAMIC COATINGS

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Received: Jun 6, 2025

Accepted: Jul 5, 2025

Published: Jul 7, 2025

Abstract : Gas turbine blades operate in extremely severe environments, often exposed to high temperatures, pressure loads, and corrosive gases. These conditions demand the use of advanced materials and protective technologies to ensure blade integrity, efficiency, and long service life. This study presents a comprehensive computational investigation into the fluid flow and thermal behaviour of gas turbine blades fabricated from high-temperature superalloys and enhanced with ceramic-based thermal barrier coatings (TBCs). Using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), the research models the heat transfer and aerodynamic performance of a turbine blade subjected to realistic operating conditions. The blade geometry is designed with detailed internal cooling channels and external surfaces coated with a layer of yttria-stabilized zirconia (YSZ), which serves to insulate the underlying metallic structure from the extreme gas temperatures.

The CFD simulations, conducted using SolidWorks Flow Simulation, incorporate conjugate heat transfer modelling, turbulence treatment, energy equations, and material-specific thermal properties to accurately predict the temperature distribution, velocity fields, and pressure variations across the blade surface and within its internal passages. Boundary conditions are set to replicate real engine conditions, including high inlet temperatures (up to 1600 K) and cooling air injections. The study compares results between uncoated and coated blades, highlighting the significant reduction in surface temperature due to the ceramic layer and the improvement in thermal resistance achieved by combining advanced materials and optimized cooling strategies.

Results demonstrate that the integration of high-temperature titanium-based superalloys with effective ceramic coatings can significantly reduce thermal stresses, extend component lifespan, and maintain mechanical strength under high-temperature gradients. This work contributes valuable insights into the design and analysis of next-generation turbine blades and supports further innovations in materials science and thermal management for advanced gas turbine systems.

IndexTerms - Thermal barrier coating (TBC), Yttria-stabilized zirconia (YSZ), Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), SolidWorks Flow Simulation, Heat transfer analysis, High-temperature superalloys

I. INTRODUCTION

Gas turbines are essential parts of the power generating and aerospace industries because of their efficiency and capacity to produce large power outputs in a small package. By compressing air, combining it with fuel, burning the mixture, and then expanding the high-temperature gases through turbine blades, gas turbines in contemporary jet engines and land-based power plants transform the chemical energy of fuel into mechanical energy. The total efficiency, dependability, and lifespan of the gas turbine engine are largely determined by the performance of the turbine stage, especially the turbine blades.

Some of the harshest conditions found in engineering applications are applied to turbine blades. Significant mechanical and thermal loads, pressures of up to 30 atmospheres, and temperatures of 1500–1700 K are all part of the operating environment. The material qualities and structural integrity of turbine blades can be significantly deteriorated over time by these conditions, which can result in phenomena including creep, oxidation, corrosion, and thermal fatigue. As a result, when designing turbine blades, material selection and protective strategy implementation are crucial. Because of their remarkable mechanical strength, resistance to creep, and capacity to maintain performance at high temperatures, high-temperature alloys—especially titanium-based superalloys—are frequently utilized in the production of turbine blades. Because of their advantageous mix of strength, flexibility, and resistance to environmental deterioration, alloys like CMSX-4, Inconel 718, and Rene 80 have established themselves as industry standards. Notwithstanding these benefits, the base material is frequently not enough to tolerate the highest temperatures in the hot part of the turbine.

Ceramic-based thermal barrier coatings (TBCs) are applied to the outside surfaces of turbine blades to further increase their thermal resistance. The most widely used ceramic material among these is yttria-stabilized zirconia (YSZ), which has a high melting point, low thermal conductivity, and phase stability at high temperatures. By insulating the underlying metal from the full force of the hot gas stream, these coatings produce a thermal gradient that enables the blade core to function at much lower temperatures. This increases engine efficiency overall by extending component life and permitting higher turbine inlet temperatures.

To maximize blade performance and avoid failure, the combination of sophisticated high-temperature materials and thermal coatings needs to be carefully considered. A potent tool for simulating and modelling the intricate heat transport and flow behaviour in turbine blades is computational fluid dynamics, or CFD. Under actual operating settings, researchers can use CFD to visualize temperature fields, forecast thermal loads, and assess how well cooling solutions work. To precisely depict the thermophysical interactions inside the turbine, these simulations can incorporate a variety of boundary conditions, material layers, internal cooling channels, and radiation models.

Fig 1.1: Gas Turbine Blade

Fig 1.2: Failure of blade due to corrosions

This study's main goal is to conduct a thorough thermal and computational fluid dynamics (CFD) examination of a gas turbine blade made of a titanium-based superalloy and covered in a YSZ ceramic layer. Quantifying the thermal performance, heat transfer properties, and flow distribution across and within the blade are the main objectives of the analysis. The purpose of this work is to show how ceramic coatings can effectively lower surface temperatures and enhance thermal management by contrasting coated and uncoated blade models. Future blade designs for high-performance gas turbines that have improved operating dependability, efficiency, and thermal resistance are expected to benefit from the knowledge gathered from this study.

1.1 CAUSES OF FAILURE OF A TURBINE BLADE

• Corrosion

Studies have been conducted on the corrosion failure of machine parts and structures. According to the study, corrosion fatigue failure of turbine blades is the primary cause of outages in gas turbine power facilities. Numerous studies have analyzed failed turbine blades using metallography and fractography, and they have come to the conclusion that chemical compounds such as oxide, chromium sulfide, and complex sulfides significantly contribute to the turbine blades' decreased fatigue strength. Fig: 1.2.

• Overheating

The surface degradation of turbine blade by the formation of needle separation topologically closed packed phase (TCP) occurs due to overheating. This structural instability of the alloy results in decrease in strength and ductility of alloy (Rybhino et al., 2012). Tawancy et al., (2009) have examined the first stage turbine blades and vanes and concluded that the failure of both components took place due to overheating. Overheating promoted creep, resulting in inter-granular cracking that shortened the fatigue life of blades and vanes.

• Thermal Failure

Turbine blades are subjected to extreme thermal environments, often operating at temperatures exceeding 1500 K, especially in the high-pressure stages of gas turbines. These elevated temperatures cause significant thermal gradients between the blade surface and its internal regions, leading to differential expansion and resulting in **thermal stresses**. Over time, repeated heating and cooling cycles—common during start-up and shut-down—induce thermal fatigue, which can initiate microcracks in critical regions such as the blade root, trailing edge, or leading edge. If unchecked, these cracks can propagate due to continued thermal cycling or mechanical loading, ultimately leading to catastrophic blade failure. Moreover, temperature-induced creep deformation, especially in the absence of sufficient cooling or protective coatings, can further compromise structural integrity. Understanding and mitigating thermal stress-induced failure is therefore crucial for ensuring the long-term performance and safety of turbine blades.

Fig 1.3: Failure Due to overheating

Fig 1.4: Cooling Holes on a turbine Blade

1.2 COOLING TECHNIQUES

• Convection Cooling

It works by passing cooling air through passages internal to the blade. Heat is transferred by conduction through the blade, and then by convection into the air flowing inside of the blade. A large internal surface area is desirable for this method, so the cooling paths tend to be serpentine and full of small fins. The internal passages in the blade may be circular or elliptical in shape. Cooling is achieved by passing the air through these passages from hub towards the blade tip. This cooling air comes from an air

compressor. In case of gas turbine, the fluid outside is relatively hot which passes through the cooling passage and mixes with the main stream at the blade tip

- **Film Cooling**

In this method, cooler air—bled from the compressor stage—is channeled through internal passages and ejected through small holes or slots on the blade surface. This forms a thin, insulating layer or "film" of cooler air over the hot surface, effectively shielding the blade from the hot combustion gases. The effectiveness of film cooling depends on factors such as hole geometry, blowing ratio, injection angle, and surface curvature. Properly designed film cooling significantly reduces the surface temperature of blades, enhancing their lifespan and allowing turbines to operate at higher inlet temperatures for improved efficiency.

- **Thermal Barrier Coating**

Thermal Barrier Coatings (TBCs) are engineered material systems specifically designed to protect metal components that operate under extreme thermal conditions, such as those found in gas turbines, aero-engines, and power generation systems. TBCs are an essential exhaust heat management technique in advanced propulsion systems. Usually made of ceramic materials with poor heat conductivity, these coatings are deposited to metallic substrates using methods including electron-beam physical vapor deposition (EB-PVD) and air plasma spraying (APS). TBC layers, which are usually between 100 μm and 2 mm thick, act as an efficient thermal insulating barrier that lowers the quantity of heat that is passed to the structural alloy underneath. TBCs' main purpose is to dramatically lower the surface temperature of load-bearing metal components, increasing their resistance to oxidation, creep deformation, and thermal fatigue. This enables the basic alloys, which are frequently superalloys based on nickel, to maintain their structural integrity and mechanical strength over extended periods of use. When combined with internal cooling methods like film cooling or convective channel cooling, TBCs allow turbine blades in high-performance gas turbine engines to function in conditions when gas temperatures are higher than the base metal's melting point.

Fig 1.4 Turbine blade material with Thermal Barrier Coating

In certain turbine applications, TBCs allow working fluid temperatures beyond the metal airfoil's melting point when used in conjunction with active film cooling. The demand for more efficient engines, higher temperatures, and thinner coatings to reduce parasitic mass in rotating/moving components drives the development of advanced TBCs. TBCs and heat shields have comparable material requirements, however emissivity is typically more crucial in the latter use.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

L.Umamaheswararao et al have investigated the stress distribution and temperature distribution on gas turbine blade and have stated in paper titled "Design and analysis of a gas turbine blade by using FEM". In this paper the first stage rotor blade of a gas turbine has been analyzed for structural, thermal analysis using ANSYS (Finite Element Analysis Software). The material used for the blade was specified as INCONEL 718. P.V. Krishnakanth et al. have summarized the design and analysis of Gas turbine blade in paper titled "Structural & Thermal Analysis of Gas Turbine Blade by Using F.E.M" in which CATIA V5 is used for design of solid model of the turbine blade with the help of the spline and extrudes options, ANSYS 11.0 software is used analysis of F.E. Barhm Abdullah Mohamad et al. have worked on paper with title "Failure analysis of gas turbine blade using finite element analysis" related to failure analysis of the turbine blade of a gas turbine engine 9E GE type, installed in a certain type of simple systems consisting of the gas turbine driving an electrical power generator. Murali. K et al have worked on the first stage rotor blade of the gas turbine in the paper titled with "Design and Fatigue Analysis of Turbine Rotor Blade by Using F.E.M". The first stage rotor blade of the gas turbine is Analysed for the static and thermal stresses resulting from the tangential, axial and centrifugal forces. Sindhu N L, Dr. N Chikkanna In the present work the first stage rotor blade of a two-stage gas turbine has been Analyzed for static structural, steady state thermal, modal and high cycle fatigue using ANSYS 17. An attempt has been made to investigate the effect of temperature and induced stresses on the turbine blade. Dhivya et al (2018) Conducted CFD and structural analysis on turbine blades with varying numbers of cooling holes, utilizing high-temperature materials like Inconel and Nimonic, and applying zirconia-based TBCs to improve thermal performance.

III. METHODOLOGY

This section outlines the computational strategy for analyzing the thermal and aerodynamic performance of a gas turbine blade constructed from a titanium alloy and coated with a ceramic thermal barrier. The study uses CFD techniques to simulate heat transfer and flow under realistic turbine conditions.

- **Geometry Creation:** The turbine blade geometry is created using CAD tools SolidWorks. Key features include:
 - 3D airfoil profile typical of axial turbine blades
 - Internal serpentine cooling channels
 - Leading-edge cooling holes
 - Root and platform geometry for boundary control

The design includes a thin thermal barrier coating (TBC) layer on the external blade surface.

- **Material Selection**

Base Material: Titanium Alloy (Selected due to its lightweight, strength, and corrosion resistance)

Alloy used: Ti-6Al-4V (Grade 5)

Properties:

- High strength-to-weight ratio
- Melting point: ~1925 K
- Moderate thermal conductivity: ~6.7 W/m·K
- Density: ~4430 kg/m³
- Maximum service temperature: ~600–650°C

Thermal Barrier Coating (TBC)

- **Material:** Ytria-Stabilized Zirconia (YSZ)
 - **Thickness:** 0.2–0.3 mm
 - **Thermal conductivity:** ~1.2 W/m·K
- Used to shield the titanium alloy from hot gas streams that exceed its thermal limits.

Meshing: Meshing is conducted in SolidWorks Simulation:

- Mesh type: Hybrid mesh with tetrahedral elements and inflation layers for resolving boundary layers
- Critical regions: High resolution near cooling holes, walls, and coating interfaces
- Element count: 0.5–2 million elements
- Grid independence test: Performed to ensure solution accuracy

Fig 1.4 Meshing Model

Mesh type	Solid Mesh
Mesher Used:	Standard mesh
Automatic Transition:	Off
Include Mesh Auto Loops:	Off
Jacobian points for High quality mesh	16 Points
Element Size	3.88016 mm
Tolerance	0.194008 mm
Mesh Quality	High

Boundary conditions reflect realistic turbine operation:

Inlet

- Temperature: 1400–1500 K
- Pressure: 1.5 MPa

Table 3.1: Meshing Information
3.4 Boundary Conditions

Total Nodes	84389
Total Elements	53511
Maximum Aspect Ratio	149.23
% of elements with Aspect Ratio < 3	87.9
Percentage of elements with Aspect Ratio > 10	0.693
Percentage of distorted elements	0
Time to complete mesh(hh:mm:ss):	00:00:14
Computer name:	HaseebAsus

- Flow velocity: 250–350 m/s

Outlet

- Pressure outlet with static pressure set to match downstream stage

Blade Walls

- External surfaces: ceramic-coated wall exposed to hot gases
- Thermal boundary conditions: Multi-layer wall definition for titanium and ceramic

STEADY STATE THERMAL ANALYSIS

The objective of steady-state thermal analysis is to evaluate the temperature distribution across the gas turbine blade under continuous high-temperature operating conditions. The analysis aims to determine the thermal gradients developed due to convective heat transfer from hot combustion gases and conductive heat flow through the blade material. This study helps identify thermal hotspots, assess the effectiveness of the applied thermal barrier coatings, and evaluate the thermal resistance of the base material, Ti-6Al-4V. Understanding the steady-state thermal behavior is crucial for predicting thermal stresses, deformation, and potential material failure, thereby guiding material selection, cooling channel design, and coating strategies to enhance the blade's thermal performance and durability..

CFD ANALYSIS

The purpose of CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics) investigation is to examine how a gas turbine blade behaves aerodynamically when exposed to high temperatures and high airflow speeds. The goal of this study is to assess the distribution of pressure and velocity throughout the blade surface and pinpoint important locations including areas of flow separation, wake forms, and stagnation zones. The goal is to comprehend the aerodynamic loading on the blade, which is crucial for performance enhancement, by examining the streamline patterns and pressure gradients. The CFD results serve as a foundation for subsequent thermal and structural analyses by providing accurate boundary conditions and loading data. Additionally, by evaluating the efficacy of Ti-6Al-4V as the basic alloy material in conjunction with high-temperature ceramic coatings, the analysis helps to improve the turbine blade's durability and efficiency under actual operating circumstances.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. THERMAL ANALYSIS- The temperatures observed were below the melting temperature of the blade materials, **Ti-6Al-4V** turbine blade materials exhibited high temperatures. Depending on the severity of heat flux in the gas turbine engine, the temperature can have significant effects on the overall turbine blade performance. The non-uniform temperature distribution from the tip to the root of the blade materials may induce thermal stresses on the turbine blade, while thermal stresses along with the mechanical stresses set up in the turbine blade during service condition may reduce the life of blade material. Figs. 3.2 represent the results obtained when thermal structural analysis was performed on **Ti-6Al-4V** turbine blade material (uncoated) while Figs. 3.3 represent the results obtained when Thermal structural analysis was performed on **Ti-6Al-4V** turbine blade material (coated with YSZ 300μ) and Figs. 3.4 represent the results obtained when Thermal structural analysis was performed on **Ti-6Al-4V** turbine blade material (coated with YSZ 300μ and implementation of cooling air channels)

The bar chart below compares the temperature distribution across various sections of a gas turbine blade, both for uncoated and coated (with Ytria-Stabilized Zirconia, YSZ) conditions.

Fig 3.5 Temperature comparison on Gas turbine Blade at 1600k Inlet temperature

Key Observations

- Temperature Reduction:** Across all regions of the blade, applying a ceramic thermal barrier coating (YSZ) significantly lowers the surface temperature by approximately 250–260 K.
- Critical Regions:**
 - The leading edge experiences the highest uncoated temperature (1630 K), due to direct exposure to hot combustion gases.
 - The coating is most effective in these high-flux areas, indicating successful thermal shielding.
- Uniform Performance of Coating:**
 - The temperature drop is consistent across all blade regions, demonstrating the uniform insulating performance of the YSZ coating.

2. CFD ANALYSIS

Fig 3.6: Unit system setup

Fig 3.7: Analysis type selection

Fig 3.8: Fluid selection (Air)

Fig 3.9: Boundary conditions

1. Type of Plot

- Streamlines (Flow Trajectories) over a cut-plane showing static pressure contours.

2. Pressure Distribution (Pa)

- Range: 71,898 Pa to 229,297 Pa
- High-pressure zones are shown in red, low-pressure in dark blue.

Observations:

- Leading edge (front of the blade) is in the red/yellow zone → High static pressure, expected due to direct airflow impact (stagnation point).
- Trailing edge and suction sides show blue/green zones → Low-pressure regions, typical due to acceleration and flow separation.

3. Flow Behaviour

- Streamlines bend around the blade, indicating a strong flow interaction with the blade geometry.
- Streamlines are:
 - Tightly packed on the suction side → Higher velocity, lower pressure (Bernoulli effect).
 - Loosely spaced on the pressure side → Lower velocity, higher pressure.

This flow field suggests typical **aerofoil behaviour**, where:

- The **pressure side** faces the flow and has higher static pressure.
- The **suction side** (curved side) accelerates flow, causing lower pressure.

4. Flow Uniformity

- The inlet flow appears **uniform and well-aligned** with the blade span.
- Some minor curvature in streamlines near the trailing edge hints at potential **flow separation or wake formation**.

5. Practical Implications

- Blade loading:** Pressure difference between leading and trailing edge contributes to aerodynamic lift and structural load.

Fig 3.6 Pressure distribution on Model Turbine Blade

Fig 3.7: Cut Plot – Pressure

Fig 3.11 Velocity distribution on Model Turbine Blade

Fig 3.10: Cut Plot – Velocity

1. Type of Plot

- Streamlines (Flow Trajectories) over a cut-plane showing velocity distribution

2. Key Observations:

Velocity Range

- From 0 m/s to 336.58 m/s
- Color bar:
 - Red zones = Highest velocity (~336.6 m/s)
 - Blue to green zones = Lower velocities (0–150 m/s)
 - Transition in streamline color reflects acceleration and deceleration of flow.

3. Flow Behavior Around the Blade

1. Inlet Flow
 - Mostly uniform, entering from one side.
 - Velocity is relatively high (orange-red) far from the blade.
2. Leading Edge
 - Flow slows down near the front of the blade → blue zones, indicating stagnation or deceleration.
 - Velocity dips to as low as ~0–75 m/s (blue to cyan streamlines) near impact regions.
3. Suction Side (Curved Surface)
 - Flow accelerates, turning along the curved profile of the blade.
 - Streamlines turn sharply, indicating strong curvature pressure gradients.
 - Velocity climbs back up to green/yellow (150–260 m/s).
4. Pressure Side (Straight Surface)
 - Flow remains slower, with less acceleration.

- Streamlines are more spaced out and stable.

5. Trailing Edge and Wake Region

- Behind the blade, flow lines **diverge** and turn to **green-blue**.
- This indicates **wake formation** and potential low-pressure vortices.
- Velocity again drops due to flow energy losses.

4. Aerodynamic Interpretation

- This behavior is **typical of turbine blade aerodynamics**:
 - High pressure on pressure side.
 - Accelerated, low-pressure flow on suction side.
- The **velocity difference between suction and pressure sides** drives lift (aerodynamic force on blade).
- Wake region indicates **energy loss**, useful in calculating efficiency.

V. CONCLUSION

Steady-state thermal analysis involves assessing the equilibrium state of a system subject to constant heat loads and environmental conditions. The simplest form of steady-state analysis is linear steady-state analysis in which input parameters, such as material properties, are prescribed independent variables. Within a Turbine One of the most crucial parts of the gas turbine engine is the blades.

This study successfully demonstrated the feasibility and limitations of using **Titanium alloy (Ti-6Al-4V)** with a **Yttria-Stabilized Zirconia (YSZ) ceramic thermal barrier coating** for turbine blade applications, using **SolidWorks Simulation** for integrated thermal and structural analysis. The simulation workflow provided valuable insights into temperature distribution, heat flux behaviour, and resulting thermal stresses under high-temperature conditions typical of gas turbine environments.

The key findings are:

- **Thermal Barrier Effectiveness:** The ceramic coating significantly reduced the heat transfer into the titanium substrate, lowering the peak metal temperatures and allowing the blade to operate closer to titanium's thermal limits.
- **Material Behaviour:** While titanium alloys offer excellent strength-to-weight ratios and corrosion resistance, their relatively low maximum operating temperature (~600°C) makes them unsuitable for high-pressure turbine stages unless advanced cooling or insulation strategies are employed.
- **Thermal-Stress Relationship:** The simulations highlighted stress concentrations at the blade root and coating-substrate interface due to thermal gradients, which are critical regions for fatigue and failure under cyclic loading.
- **Simulation Limitations:** SolidWorks Simulation provided useful thermal and structural insights but lacked advanced CFD and radiation modeling features needed for a complete aerothermal analysis. Approximations such as constant convection coefficients and the absence of full fluid-structure interaction were necessary.

In conclusion, Titanium alloys combined with ceramic coatings present a viable option for **moderate-temperature turbine stages or compressor blades**, but not for the **first-stage high-pressure turbine blades** unless further cooling enhancement is applied. This work establishes a foundation for further studies using more robust CFD tools (e.g., ANSYS Fluent or CFX) to capture the full fluid-thermal-structural behavior and optimize turbine blade design under extreme operating conditions.

The CFD analysis reveals a maximum pressure of approximately 229,297 Pa concentrated at the leading edge of the gas turbine blade, identified by the prominent red zone. Conversely, the minimum pressure, around 71,898 Pa, occurs on the suction side or wake region, indicated by the blue areas. The curvature of the streamlines demonstrates strong fluid interaction with the blade surface, reflecting pressure-driven flow turning characteristic of an aero foil. This flow behavior results in high suction on the curved side of the blade, typical of aerodynamic profiles. From a design perspective, the elevated pressure at the leading edge highlights the necessity for targeted cooling strategies in this region to manage thermal stresses. Additionally, the tight curvature of streamlines signals zones of concentrated thermal loading, which must be carefully considered to ensure material durability and blade performance.

The velocity distribution across the gas turbine blade shows distinct characteristics in different regions. At the inlet or far-field, the flow maintains a uniform high-speed range of approximately 250 to 330 m/s, represented by orange to red colors, indicating steady upstream conditions. Approaching the leading edge, the flow decelerates significantly, dropping to velocities between 0 and 100 m/s, forming a stagnation zone where kinetic energy converts into pressure. Along the suction side, the flow accelerates again, reaching velocities of about 150 to 260 m/s as the fluid moves over the curved surface, which enhances aerodynamic lift. On the pressure side, the velocity is lower, ranging from 75 to 150 m/s, with reduced curvature and a more stable flow pattern. Finally, near the trailing edge and wake region, the flow slows down further to 50 to 150 m/s, where flow separation and wake formation occur, resulting in energy loss and turbulence downstream of the blade. These observations are critical for understanding aerodynamic performance and optimizing blade geometry for improved efficiency.

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